

Structural and electrical conductivity behaviour of cationic exchanged Y-zeolites

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The electrical conductivity, XRD, IR and uv-vis spectra of the cationic exchanged Co^{II} -, Fe^{II} - and Cu^{II} -Y-zeolites, prepared by ion exchange, are reported. The electrical conductivity data are correlated with the electronic structures, state of the cations and the properties of these catalysts, which exhibit different semiconducting behaviour.

One of the modification factors in the importance of zeolites as catalysts, is their ability to accommodate a wide variety of chemical modifications with relative ease whilst retaining their open structures. Introduction of cations into zeolite framework modifies the catalytic performance of molecular sieving action of the zeolite¹. Ion exchange can be employed to place cations into very specific framework sites so as to create small volumes of high electrostatic field. These fields are active sites to which an organic reactant molecule can be attracted, thus promoting the bond distortion and rupture essential to molecular rearrangements². Another feature of ion exchange is that it provides a route for the introduction of metal cations with view to their subsequent reduction to metal particles³.

Oxides of transition elements are catalytically interesting semiconductors⁴; unlike metals, electronic bands do not overlap but form separated regions. The most successful treatment of semiconductor catalysis was given by Vol'kenstein, who evaluated a theory concerning the crystallite size and its influence on semiconductor electronics⁵. In recent years, a large amount of attention has been directed towards understanding of catalytic activity with semiconductors. Some consideration of surface geometry, orbital availability, dispersion and symmetry at adsorption sites (uniform or non-uniform surface) will be necessary for greater understanding the conductivity that occurs through the transition oxides doped on different substrates.

This paper is devoted to the study of the properties, chemical structures and sizes of cationic exchanged (Cu^{II} , Co^{II} and Fe^{II})-Y-zeolite and their influences on the electrical conductivity behaviour.

Results and Discussion

The mode of bonding, in the mid-infrared region of the parent Y-zeolite reveals the most intense internal tetrahedron vibrations at 950–1200 and at 420–500 cm^{-1} (of T-O bending vibrations). At about 710–780 cm^{-1} , the T-O symmetric stretching is observed and the more specific lattice

vibrations are located at 570 cm^{-1} (double rings vibration). The spectra of cationic exchanged Y-zeolite reflect new bands at 640 and 500 cm^{-1} and a band at 880 cm^{-1} for Fe^{II} -Y.

The band at 640 cm^{-1} is only detected when the monolayer coverage is achieved; these surface species diffuse into the support to build bulk Ni^{II} -, Co^{II} - and Fe^{II} - Al_2O_4 especially when subjected to high temperatures.

The band at 530–500 cm^{-1} can be assigned to $\nu_{\text{M-O}}$ vibrations within the oxide layer⁶. Such low frequency shifts found on introduction of Co^{II} , Fe^{II} and Cu^{II} ions for both 640 and 500–530 cm^{-1} bands, may confirm their presence in tetrahedron network of layer silicates, as in synthetic Fe^{III} -flogopite⁷. The 880 cm^{-1} band of Fe^{II} -Y catalyst which attributes to FeO vibration⁸, confirms the introduction of Fe^{II} ions into the regions of antisymmetrical valence vibrations of T-O bonds.

As it is obvious that the framework distortion is minimal because of the dehydration step carried out before measurements. The significant shift of the 640 cm^{-1} band to a longer wavenumber in the Co^{II} -Y catalyst (660 cm^{-1}), can be deduced from the uv-vis spectra.

Absorption at 15000 cm^{-1} is characteristic of optical spectra of Co^{II} bearing zeolite samples of Y-type which testifies to the presence of tetrahedral coordinated Co^{II} ions. The color of the cationic exchanged-Y, peak positions and their assignments are listed in Table 1. The parent Y-zeolite sample of white color, shows an almost flat spectrum.

The peak position of Cu^{II} -Y indicates that Cu^{II} may be octahedrally coordinated while the broadness reveals a tetragonal distortion inside the zeolite framework.

Co^{II} -Y depicts a shoulder in the near-IR region besides two absorption bands in the visible region. The first band contains two overlapped peaks, assigned to ν_2 and ν_3 , while the second band is attributed to charge transfer.

The typical doublet band of hexa- Fe^{II} complexes are shown in the spectrum of Fe^{II} -Y. Thus one could suggest

Table 1. Color and electronic spectral data of cationic exchanged Y-zeolite

Zeolite	Color	λ_{\max} cm ⁻¹	Assignment
Cu ^{II} -Y	Blue	20000	$2T_{2g} \leftarrow 2E_g$
Co ^{II} -Y	Rose	8465	$4T_{2g} \leftarrow 4T_{1g}(v_1)$
		13300	$4A_{2g} \leftarrow 4T_{1g}(v_2)$
		15151	$4T_{1g}(P) \leftarrow T_{1g}(v_3)$
		25000	CT
Fe ^{II} -Y	Yellow	8032	$5E_g \leftarrow 5T_{2g}$
		13658	

that Fe^{II} has an octahedral structure.

Structural information is also provided by X-ray diffraction analysis. A new peak at $2\theta = 26^\circ$ is observed in the cationic exchanged Y-zeolite, and is assigned to M-O bonds. The peaks due to Y-framework of $2\theta = (12, 14 \text{ and } 16^\circ)$ show a significant increase in intensity upon addition of cations. This reflects the increase of crystallinity upon modification. This peak enhancement is very clear in Co^{II}-Y catalyst.

These cationic exchanged Y-zeolite may be said isomorphous, since they nearly have the same crystallinity but different ions. This small distortion in the zeolite framework obtained as a result of cationic exchanged Y is also reflected by the minor changes in breadth and position for internal tetrahedral vibrations near 1000, 710–780 and 450 cm⁻¹ estimated from the IR data. This minimum distortion depends on the precalcination step which seems to inhibit particle growth. The nearly similar behaviour of Cu^{II}-Y compared with the parent-Y zeolite reflects the minimum distortion caused by Cu^{II} cations upon exchanging with the framework of Y.

The electrical conduction may occur through the movement of either electrons or ions, and the following basic equation may be employed,

$$\sigma = qn\mu$$

where the conductivity σ is analysed into three parameters: the charge q , concentration n and the drift mobility μ of the charge carriers. Fig. 1 depicts the qualitative dependence of $\log \sigma$ on $1/T$ for cationic Y-zeolite. The values of the activation energies are listed in Table 2. The observed linear behaviour indicates that the conductivity of the Y-zeolite obeys the relation,

$$\sigma = \sigma^* \exp(-E/KT)$$

where σ^* is a constant and E the activation energy.

Fig. 1. Electrical conductivity of Y-zeolite exchanged with divalent metal cations (O) Co^{II}-Y, (□) Fe^{II}-Y, (☆) Cu^{II}-Y (*) Y (parent zeolite)

It is obvious that the conductivity increases as the temperature rises, i.e. typical semiconductor behaviour. A phase transition was observed in all the investigated cationic exchanged-Y zeolite except the Cu^{II}-Y which showed only one phase transition with relatively low activation energy. It is apparent that the conductivity of the parent zeolite is greater than those of the cationic exchanged ones.

Table 2. Electrical conductivity data of cationic exchanged Y-zeolite

Zeolite	T K	E_1 eV	E_2 eV	σ_1 at 350 K	σ_2 at 500 K
Y-zeolite	500	0.028	0.5	5.01×10^{-8}	2.18×10^{-7}
Co ^{II} -Y	423	0.30	0.87	1.20×10^{-12}	1.26×10^{-9}
Fe ^{II} -Y	373	0.13	0.56	1.58×10^{-12}	5.01×10^{-9}
Cu ^{II} -Y	-	0.50	-	6.3×10^{-13}	7.94×10^{-10}

At high temperatures, the proton mobility, pore dimension, electrical field inside the pore system and structure reorganization must have been changed during the temperature flow and since the most active units in the zeolite framework are the hydroxyl groups, enhancement of the conductivity, with very low activation energy, is expected. Therefore, a continuous decrease in conductivity for the cationic exchanged Y-zeolite is obtained as a result of the stability of these structures.

Generally, the activation energies E_2 of high temperature ranges are greater than E_1 of low temperature ranges, by a factor ranging from 2.8 to 4.3 for both Co^{II} and Fe^{II} catalysts, respectively. This confirms that the high temperature conducting phase is distinguished by a higher activation energy E_2 than the lower temperature phase E_1 . As it is obvious, this is not a typical semiconductor behaviour, which

usually shows a decrease in activation energy as a result of increasing temperature.

The measured conductivity of the cationic exchanged Y-zeolite decreases in the following order : $\text{Fe}^{\text{II}} > \text{Co}^{\text{II}} > \text{Cu}^{\text{II}}$. This might be due to the difference in configuration between Co^{II} and Fe^{II} on one side and Cu^{II} on the other. The former, as evidenced from the UV data, possess an octahedral and a tetrahedral structures while the later forms only octahedral configuration.

Moreover, the greater size of atomic copper and the electronegativity compared with Co^{II} and Fe^{II} cations might be responsible for directing the reaction to proceed only in one phase and show significant decrease in conductivity. Copper ions also show a preference for the small cage sites, presumably at S_1^9 at elevated temperatures. These sites are filled at ca. 463 K for Cu^{II} ions and may be opposed for the other ions unless a higher temperature is applied. This could explain the one-phase formation of Cu^{II} ions. Furthermore, the nearly typical XRD patterns observed for Cu^{II} -Y and Y-zeolite, which reflect the minimum distortion involved by exchanged Cu^{II} cations inside the zeolite framework, might be another plausible explanation for the one-phase formation.

The mechanism of conduction of the cationic exchanged Y-zeolite can be discussed in the light of n (donor) and p (acceptor) types which can easily be created by introducing doping or exchange altrivalent cations into interstitial or cationic lattice positions. The parent Y-zeolite shows a conducting behaviour (E_1 value) in the temperature range 350–500 K. This reflects a decrease in the energy gap E_g , i.e. empty levels (acceptor) close to the valence band from which an electron is easily promoted, and the conduction occurs through the resulting hole in the valence band. The hole left by promoted electrons conducts in the opposite direction.

As a result of increasing the temperature, it seems that the E_g will also increases and this causes an enhancement in the E_2 value. Furthermore, the cationic exchanged Co^{II} - and Fe^{II} -Y zeolites created another phase since enhancement in both E_1 and E_2 values compared with the parent Y-zeolite values is significantly increased. This is a consequence to the pesence of the unpaired electrons, in both Fe^{II} and Co^{II} cations which may oppose each other and a repulsion between them occurs as a result of increasing the energy gap E_g .

Since p -type oxides are more active than n -type oxides, one can easily confirm that both Co^{II} -Y and Fe^{II} -Y are of p -type oxides. This is consistent with the UV-vis spectral data

which show a charge transfer trend for Co^{II} -Y catalyst. This is also recognized by Richardson¹⁰ who estimated that both CoO and FeO are p -type semiconductors whereas CuO may show both n - and p -types, coexisting within the same crystal.

The general mechanism emerged from the above discussion can be summarized as follows. The excess Co^{II} , Fe^{II} and Cu^{II} cations accommodated in the interstitial positions, generate energy levels that are empty (acceptor) with energy values far from the conduction band. A large amount of thermal energy is necessary for promotion and conduction where conductivity occurs via the hole in the valence band. From the above conclusion, one can say that the fermi level, which is the electrochemical potential in the midway between the highest filled and the lowest empty levels, is significantly decreased as a result of increasing acceptor levels.

Experimental

Preparation of the catalysts : Y-zeolite (Union Carbide) was converted to Cu^{II} -Y, Co^{II} -Y and Fe^{II} -Y forms by exhaustive ion exchange procedure of the parent Na^+ -Y zeolite. The experimental details are described elsewhere⁹. The chosen concentration was on the basis that the exchange procedure reaches 80%. All the samples were air-dried at 393 K for 24 h and then calcined in air at 723 K for 6 h.

Characterization of the catalysts :

X-ray analysis : All catalysts were examined by X-ray diffractometer (Philips 1390, Ni filter). The data were recorded from $2\theta = 6^\circ$ upto 40° at $2^\circ/\text{min}$ and at room temperature. The diffuse reflectance electronic spectra of the samples were measured with a Beckman DK-2A spectrophotometer at room temperatures in the oxide state after being calcined. IR spectra were recorded on Shimadzu IR-470 with a resolution of 4 cm^{-1} .

All samples were compressed to pellets (13 mm dia \times 2 mm). The measuring technique of the electrical conductivity is described elsewhere¹¹.

References

1. B. Coughlan and M. A. Keane, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1990, **68**, 1471; *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans.*, 1990, **68**, 1007.
2. P. Pichat, J. C. Vedrine, P. Gallezot and B. Imelik, *J. Catal.*, 1974, **32**, 190; E. Garbowski and H. Praliand, *J. Chim. Phys.*, 1979, **76**, 687.
3. Y. Y. Huang, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1973, **95**, 6636; M. M. Mohamed, *Spectrochim. Acta*, communicated.
4. O. V. Krylov, "Catalysis by Nonmetals", Academic, New York, 1970.

Note

5. F. F. Volkenstein, "The Electronic Theory of Catalysis on Semiconductors", Macmillan, New York, 1963.
6. D. M. Adams, "Metal, Ligand and Related Vibrations : A Critical Survey of the Infrared and Raman Spectra of Metallic and Organometallic Compounds", Edward Arnold, London, 1967.
7. V. C. Farmer, "The Infrared Spectra of Minerals", Mineral. Soc., London, 1974.
8. K. Nakamoto "Infrared and Raman Spectra of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds", Wiley, New York, 1986.
9. M. M. Mohamed, *Thermochim. Acta*, in the press.
10. J. T. Richardson, "Principles of Catalyst Development", Plenum Press, New York, 1989.
11. M. G. Abd-El Wahed and A. K. Abd-El Kader, *J. Mater. Sci. Lett.*, 1985, 4, 976.